

H2020 Work Programme

D5.7 – Report on stakeholder engagement and mobilization – first version

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This document is the BIOBEC project Report on stakeholder engagement and mobilization (contract no. 101023381) corresponding to D5.7 (M15) led by FVA. This document contains reports on the first 15 months of stakeholder engagement and mobilization, including the first IRWG workshop.

This project has received funding from the Bio-based Industries Joint Undertaking (JU) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101023381. The JU receives support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and the Bio-based Industries Consortium.

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Acronyms and abbreviations

EC	European Commission
WP	Work Package
IRWG	Implementation and Replication Working Group
BBEC	Bio-Based Education Center
MML	Mobilisation and Mutual Learning
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
EUBIONET	European Bioeconomy Network

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1.Executive summary

Stakeholder engagement and mobilization is a central part of BIObec strategy. The project seeks to set the basis for the development of Bio-Based Education Centers (BBEC) in six different European regions to answer the needs of the bio-based industry at local, regional, and national levels. These BBECs are expected to ensure a wide geographical coverage in Europe and address a wide range of topics linked to the variety of value chains and the different institutional contexts, paving the way for replication in other regions.

The core nucleus for the future implementation of the BBECs is the Implementation and Replication Working Group (IRWG), that will participate to project initiatives in the role of stakeholders and will facilitate the replication of the BIObec's experience beyond the project's efforts.

The IRWG members are local stakeholders, interested in implementing and replicating the BBECs experience in other EU Regions and countries by co-developing a roadmap applicable for potential additional BBECs across Europe.

This document describes BIObec approach for stakeholder engagement and mobilization, including the strategy to select the IRWG members, promote contacts and facilitate the debate, mutual learning, good practices exchange and collaboration on challenges towards the creation of BBECs, ensuring motivation and lively involvement of stakeholders throughout the project.

Since bioeconomy and education are typically crosscutting issues, this document also reports on the synergies and collaborations established with other projects and initiatives during the first 15 months of the project.

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2. Introduction

This deliverable reports on the actions performed under WP5 to engage and mobilise stakeholders in BIObec activities (Subtask 5.3.1) and to facilitate the debate, mutual learning, good practices exchange and collaboration on challenges towards the creation of Bio-Based Education Centres (BBECs). The first step to achieve these objectives took place through a **first Implementation and Replication Working Group (IRWG) online workshop** (Subtask 5.3.2), organised on October 2022.

These activities are strictly connected to WP1, WP2, WP3 and WP4 and exploit the results collected in the different WPs, building specifically on Task 1.1, "BIObec actors' network creation", for the identification and attraction of relevant actors/stakeholders, along value chains and at different levels. The partners, in fact, mapped the stakeholders to be involved in BIObec's workshops and events and that could be also suitable in becoming IRWG members.

This actors' network includes educational bodies, industries, public administration, civil society, political actors and other actors on a local, regional, national and at European level, including their connections and different roles in the network.

In the introduction (**chapter 2**), the document provides the objectives of the stakeholder engagement, the stakeholders already involved and contributing to the project's impact, the activities to engage them and also the risks foreseen for these activities as well as strategy to reach the expected KPIs.

Chapter 3 describes in detail the stakeholder engagement strategy defined by the responsible partners to attract and engage different actors. It also provides an overview of the target stakeholders identified and of the preparatory activities performed before their active engagement, namely the creation of a stakeholders database and the recruitment and selection of the IRWG members through the creation of a value proposition. The list of stakeholders already involved as BIObec's IRWG members is also provided in the chapter.

The first IRWG workshop is reported in **Chapter 4**, with an overview of the objectives, the strategy to attract participants, the format of the workshop and also the outcomes collected during the interactive exercise performed with the MIRO board.

Chapter 5 focuses on the synergies and collaborations established under the Task 5.4 "Liaison with other projects and initiatives", specifically the collaboration with relevant concluded and ongoing projects and initiatives, the collaboration with the European Bioeconomy Network (EuBioNet) and the collaborations established in terms of co-organisation of events and debates, participation to other projects' activities, joint communication activities and publications.

Finally, **Chapter 6** provides conclusions and the next steps planned.

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2.1. Objectives of the stakeholder engagement activities

Stakeholder engagement specific activities are connected to the design and implementation of the 6 BBECs and build on the activities performed in WP1, WP3 and WP4.

This activity aims at attracting, informing and involving stakeholders to support the design, implementation and replication of the 6 BBECs.

It promotes the engagement and mobilisation of the relevant stakeholders through a series of activities that are implemented by BIObec. Stakeholder engagement targets actors across partner and non-partner countries, addressing all relevant networks, stakeholders and valuable players in the bio-based industry and bioeconomy field that can contribute to BIObec. An early engagement of stakeholders raised awareness, enabled the timely identification of requirements, bottlenecks and challenges and enhanced the sense of ownership and acceptance of the solutions proposed (BBECs) toward an efficient exploitation. The activity benefited from the mapping activities performed in WP1 and devised the stakeholder engagement strategy of the BIObec project.

The IRWG participates to project initiatives in the role of stakeholders and is to be considered as the core nucleus for the future implementation of the BBECs as well as initiators of initiatives replicating BIObec experience beyond the project's efforts.

The liaison with Digital Innovation Hubs is also ensured and the consortium already secured 5 Letters of Support before the beginning of the project and an active action of engagement was taken to enlarge the involvement of additional ones during project implementation. A more extensive description of the IRWG is provided in paragraph 3.3.

2.2. Stakeholder engagement contributing to project's impact

The impact of the project will be maximised thanks to the coordinated involvement of a wide range of actors and stakeholders beyond the consortium partners, including the general public. Different means will be implemented in order to motivate stakeholders to contribute to the outcomes of the project as well as to communicate/disseminate them, including the establishment of the IRWG to boost future implementation. Collaboration with existing initiatives will play a key role in maximizing the impact of the project: a strong interlink with the European Bioeconomy Network and the parallel projects and initiatives like Transition2BIO, the study funded by the EC "Promoting Education, Training and Skills in the Bioeconomy" and the ICA Community of Practice for Bioeconomy Education (ICA CoP Bio-Edu) (see chapter 5) will be pivotal for replication and coordination purposes.

2.3. Activities to engage stakeholders

The stakeholders are actively involved in WP1, WP2 and WP3 activities through regional workshops in order to assess their needs and expectations as well as to understand the regional conditions as basis for the design of the BBECs.

The project's main results and work progress, success stories and best practices will be shared through 2 Stakeholders MML online webinars organised in WP5 and involving

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at least 50 participants each. The online format was chosen to attract a wider audience and registration of participants from several countries, with the objective to ensure that regions with different needs and expectations are represented, as well as involving stakeholders from regions where bioeconomy is less developed (e.g. the Central and Eastern European countries, thanks to the link with BIOEAST Initiative represented by ART). The first MML workshop already took place on October 2022 and a more extensive description is provided in chapter 4.

2.4. Risks connected to the stakeholder engagement

For all the above-mentioned specific activities, the following table resumes the risks and proposed mitigation measures identified and suggested by the responsible partners.

Description of risk	Proposed risk-mitigation measures
Lack or poor participation by stakeholders and IRWG members	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Constantly motivation through accurate incentive strategies, based on provision of information and insights and accurate explanation of potential for follow up of the project involvement of a wider group increase variety and tailoring of communication and dissemination means, including wide use of social networks and digital technologies
Poor commitment in replication by IRWG	Constant communication and envisioning of potential replication benefits and solutions; identification of further replication opportunities beyond initial members of IRWG

Table 1: Risks and mitigation measures foreseen in WP5

The proposed risk mitigation measures that are embedded in the strategic approach for the stakeholder engagement, proved to be effective in preventing possible issues during the first 15 months of the project.

2.5. KPI expected

The following table describes the KPIs foreseen for the WP and specifically for the activities related to the number of IRWG members to reach, their mobilisation and engagement through mutual learning workshops and the activity performed to keep them informed and interested in the project.

Target outcome	Means of validation	KPI	KPIs currently reached
IRWG	Number of participating stakeholders	#60	#40

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Stakeholders informed	Number of stakeholders reached	#2000	Around #1600* stakeholders through the various project's activities
IRWG Mobilisation and Mutual Learning workshop	Number of workshops organised and participants	#2 online workshops #50 stakeholders each	#1 online workshop #75 registered participants #60 participants

Table 2: KPIs foreseen in the WP

*at least 500 stakeholders invited to WP1 and WP2 activities, 1600 stakeholders reached through the BIObec's social media channels and newsletters, around 300 stakeholders invited to the 1st IRWG workshop.

Considering that some stakeholders have been informed through several activities among the above ones, we count the number related to the newsletters and social media.

According to the KPIs planned and reached in the first half of the project, we can claim that the stakeholder engagement is proceeding as planned.

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3. Stakeholder engagement strategy

3.1. BIObec target stakeholders and their involvement in the project

The BIObec stakeholders build on partner networks and organisations, in particular on the IRWG, the BIObec Advisory Board and the involvement of the Biobased Industry Consortium (BIC) members. The creation of this network is supported by the 6 BBECs leaders (Regional representatives of the studied BBECs in the consortium) and WP leaders in order to boost regional participation. The main aim is the identification and attraction of relevant actors/stakeholders, along value chains and at different levels, to the activities of this WP, WP1, WP2 and WP3, where an additional set of roll-out, replication and training events will be conducted.

This actor's network includes educational bodies, industries, public administration, civil society, political actors and other actors on a local, regional, national and at European level including their connections and different roles in the network.

There are also other types of stakeholders present in the regions, such as associations, hubs, public-private partnerships, advisors and vocational institutions. These actors have been mapped during WP1 and WP2 activities and their connection with the 6 BBECs is presented in the figure below (details on [D1.3](#)).

Figure 1: Type of stakeholders per each BBEC

3.2. Creation of the stakeholder database

The creation of the stakeholder database took place in connection with Task 1.1, "BIObec actors' network creation", for the identification and attraction of relevant actors/stakeholders targeted along different domains (see 3.1). The collection of stakeholders was created in the BIObec private shared point without disclosing any personal data and in compliance with GDPR. For this reason, the partners mapped the different stakeholders listing the organisation/institution name, the types of stakeholders identified (e.g. educational bodies, industries, public administration, civil society, political actors and other), the Country in which the stakeholders operate, also defining their potential/actual involvement in the project (e.g. if they are already members of the IRWG) and the BIObec partner responsible for their engagement and direct contact.

Currently, the stakeholder database counts around 760 stakeholders mapped.

3.3. The Implementation and Replication Working Group (IRWG) and its involvement in BIObec

The project established a network named Implementation and Replication Working Group (IRWG) in order to support its implementation, through the education Centres and guarantee the replicability of the BBEC experience in other European regions and countries through a process of stakeholder engagement and the co-development of a roadmap applicable for potential additional BBECs across Europe and beyond. Stakeholders relevant for the IRWG are committed through letters of support. This network is set up and mobilized in WP5, and its contribution is leveraged in all other WPs.

Multi-stakeholders IRWG involves actors across partner and non-partner Countries, will participate to project initiatives in the role of stakeholders and will be the core component of the future implementation of the BBECs. The IRWG will involve Regions and BioRegions, industrial clusters, educational providers at different levels (covering vocational training, university and post-university curricula, on-the-job training and lifelong learning), NGOs and associations of primary producers, etc.

The project is aligned with the vision of innovating the bio-based education framework through an integrated multisectoral and multi-stakeholder strategy.

Specifically, the involvement of the Members of the IRWG concerns:

- participation in project's workshops by delivering information on current needs and potential solutions;
- collaboration in the exploitation of the results of the project by exploring the opportunity to transfer the provided novel education framework into the territorial bioeconomy ecosystem;
- collaboration to the dissemination of the project results and communication materials through its channels.

The project foresaw 2 online IRWG workshops/webinars (on M8 and M20) to be organised under WP5 responsibility, involving at least 50 participants each (see 2.5), to stimulate the discussion around bioeconomy education, to define a more integrated, connected and wider approach for the BBECs future implementation.

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After an internal discussion to align this task with WP1, WP2 and WP3 progress, the consortium decided to postpone the first IRWG workshop to October (M13, see chapter 4) instead of M8. The initial foreseen context (BBI JU Stakeholder Forum) was not an option anymore, because in 2022 the event didn't take place due to the transformation of the Joint undertaking from BBI JU to CBE JU.

The second IRWG international workshop will pave the way towards the adoption and exploitation of the BIObec project and in particular, the implementation and replication of the BBECs by the stakeholders engaged.

3.3.1. Recruiting and selection of the IRWG members

During the preparation of the proposal, 35 stakeholders interested in being involved in the project signed the Letter of Support (see Annex 1).

In order to attract additional stakeholders to be recruited as new IRWG members, during the project's implementation the following steps are defined:

- Continuous mapping of relevant stakeholders and their potential interest and motivation in being part of the IRWG
- Creation of a value proposition (see 3.3.2) to explain the objectives and benefits of the IRWG
- Identify the potential BBEC of reference in order to ensure that the challenges addressed are also relevant to the regional reality of the stakeholders
- Make sure that the stakeholders are involved in BIObec activities that are relevant for them, creating a community around bioeconomy education
- Identify among the stakeholders involved the ones that have specific interests in implementing and replicating BIObec's methodological approach in their region
- Engage these stakeholders in IRWG workshops and dedicated meetings to keep them informed and interested
- Invite them to formally express their interest by signing the Letter of Support.

The Letter of Support is not submitted to all the stakeholders who participated in BIObec activities but only to those that, after an assessment of the potential as active actors/partners in a specific regional BBEC or in the Pan-European coordination, have been found valuable for at least one of the main phases of the project: BBEC design; BBEC assessment; BBEC implementation; BBEC replication.

3.3.2. Value proposition to attract IRWG members

In order to attract new IRWG members, the responsible partner FVA created a value proposition and communication package.

The value proposition gives an overview on the project's objectives, presents the BBECs and the target stakeholders to be involved in the IRWG for their implementation and exploitation. It also provides benefits for the participating stakeholders in being members of the IRWG, namely:

- "Make their voice heard" in the design of the multi-level Bio-Based Education Centers (BBECs), by providing their expectations, needs, requirements, opportunities and barriers.

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- Make sure that the BIObec project's outcomes are actionable in their context, considering present and future needs of the industry and of the surrounding ecosystem at local, regional, national and/or international levels.
- Get first-hand insights with regards to the setup of bioeconomy education centres and have direct access to good practices and case studies in different European Countries
- Have the possibility to be engaged in the co-design of the BBEC in 6 European Countries towards wide implementation and replication of the format in different countries and levels (local, regional, national).

The value proposition document is attached in Annex 2.

3.3.3. List of stakeholders involved in BIObec's IRWG

Currently, 40 stakeholders are already official members of BIObec's IRWG and were involved in the project's different activities.

The following table resumes the list of IRWG members.

Name of Stakeholder	Country	Organization type
Universidad de Granada	Spain	Academia
Universidad de Jaén	Spain	Academia
Universidad de Sevilla	Spain	Academia
Szkoła Główna Gospodarstwa Wiejskiego - Warsaw University of Life Sciences	Poland	Academia
Department of Biotechnology of the University of Verona	Italy	Academia
Tralee Chamber	Ireland	Business Representative Organization
Kerline srl	Italy	Company (spin-off of the Italian National Research Council)
Digital Innovation Hub for Agriculture and Food production	Slovenia	Digital Innovation Hub
Институт за агростратегии и иновации - Institute for Agrostrategies and Innovation	Bulgaria	Digital Innovation Hub
Teknopark Istanbul – Innovation Center of Turkey	Turkey	Digital Innovation Hub
CINECA – Italian SuperComputing Inter-university Consortium	Italy	Digital Innovation Hub
Bi-Rex – Big Data Innovation & Research Excellence	Italy	Digital Innovation Hub – National Competence Centre
Digital Innovation Hub Sofia Technology Park	Bulgaria	Digital Innovation Hub

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European Bioplastics e.V.	Germany	Industrial Association
Viborg Development Council	Denmark	Industrial Association
Polska Izba Gospodarcza Energetyki Odnawialnej i Rozproszonej - Polish Economic Chamber of Renewable and Distributed Energy	Poland	Industrial Association
Dalgasgroup A/S	Denmark	Industry
Viborg Kommune – Viborg Municipality	Denmark	Local Authority / Policy Maker
Agenzia Andaluza del Conocimiento - Andalusian Knowledge Agency	Spain	Local Authority / Policy Maker
Ministerium für Ländlichen Raum und Verbraucherschutz Baden-Württemberg, Departement Bioökonomie und Innovation - Ministry of Rural Areas and Consumer Protection Baden-Württemberg, Department of Bioeconomy and Innovation	Germany	Local Authority / Policy Maker
Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports Department of Research and Development	Czech Republic	Local Authority / Policy Maker
Kerry County Council	Ireland	Local Authority / Policy Maker
Asociace vyzkumnych organizaci z.s. – AVO Association of Research Organisations	Czech Republic	National Bioeconomy Hub
Stowarzyszenie Inżynierów i Techników Przemysłu Chemicznego - Polish Association of Chemical Engineers	Poland	Professional Association
Instytut Ochrony Środowiska - Państwowego Instytutu Badawczego - Institute of Environmental Protection - National Research Institute	Poland	Research Institute
Transdisciplinarity for Urban Sustainability Transition - TrUST	Italy	Research Platform
SPSCH - Higher School of Chemistry, Brno	Czech Republic	School
IAR French Bioeconomy Cluster	France	Technology Cluster
FOOD+I	Spain	Technology Cluster
Fundacja Klaster LifeScience Kraków – Klaster LifeScience Krakow Foundation	Poland	Technology Cluster

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BLC3 Campus de Tecnologia e Inovação - Association BLC3 Technology and Innovation Campus	Portugal	Technology Cluster
DINAMICA Soc. Cons. a r.l.	Italy	Training centre
Asmildkloster Landbrugsskole - Asmildkloster Agricultural School	Denmark	Training centre
BioCentrum BioEdukacji , Fundacja Naukowej - Centre for Innovative Bioscience Education, Bioeducation Foundation	Poland	Traning centre
Stefan Batory Academy of Applied Scinces	Poland	Academia
EPRD Office for Economic Policy and Regional Development Ltd.	Poland	SME / consulting
Kielce City Hall / Investor Assistance Centre	Poland	Local Authority / Policy Maker
The Medical Unversity of Warsaw / Centre for Preclinical Research and Technology	Poland	Research Insitute / Science and Technology Transfer
Food Hub srl Società Benefit	Italy	Digital Magazine and Content Creator
CoE BBE – Centre of Expertise Biobased Economy	The Netherlands	Training centre

Table 3: List of IRWG members

The previous table identifies the actors who decided to be stably involved in the project in different phases. Following a dynamic process, the stakeholders were involved during the proposal phase, the preliminary common activities or in the activities in the scope of the regional BBECs. Hence, some actors were added in the previous table when the project was ongoing. On the other hand, some actors who signed the Letter of Support (LOS) for the project in the proposal phase but did not take part in any of the activities were removed from the table.

Moreover, in each BBEC are involved stably some stakeholders who did not sign the LOS but are active in contributing. These actors, that are not reported in Table 3, will be invited to sign the LOS.

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4. First IRWG workshop

On 21 October 2022, the First IRWG workshop was organised by partner FVA in collaboration with all partners, engaging 75 registered participants and 67 unique visitors joining the Zoom meeting throughout the workshop, with an average of 60 participants connected. Most of the participants expressed a great interest in being involved in the BIObec future activities and in becoming members of the IRWG.

The stakeholders involved covered a wide range of organisations based in Europe and operating in the bioeconomy industry, research and education sectors, namely:

- Universities
- Training organisations
- Research centers
- Ecosystem facilitators
- Industries and clusters
- Public administration
- NGOs
- NGOs

Figure 2: Infographic showing the type of organisations in which the participants of the workshop were involved

4.1. Objectives

The first IRWG workshop aimed at:

- stimulating the discussion around bioeconomy education
- defining a more integrated, connected and wider approach for the BBECs future implementation
- exploring the opportunity to transfer and replicate the BBECs formats into additional territorial bioeconomy ecosystems
- engaging additional IRWG members

4.2. Strategy to identify and attract participants

Under the coordination of partner FVA, the following activities took place in order to identify and attract participants:

- Invite the stakeholders already members of the IRWG (the ones that signed the LOS)
- Invite the stakeholders involved in focus groups and regional workshops organised under WP1 and WP2
- Identify additional stakeholders that potentially could be interested in implementing and replicating the BIObec's methodology
- Social media posts and a pop-up included on the project website to reach a higher audience

All these stakeholders have been invited through personal emails by the partners responsible for their direct contact (also considering GDPR questions). FVA prepared a concept and agenda carefully designing activities relevant for the stakeholders.

4.3. Format of the workshop

The first part of the workshop was focused on giving the participants an overview on the role of the IRWG, highlighting the most relevant EU funded projects in bioeconomy education, targeting different levels of education, and how BIObec can have a role in this domain.

The outcomes stemming from the studies conducted by BIObec on the current needs and inspirational case studies in bioeconomy education were also presented by the partners, in order to trigger the debate and in light of the potential involvement of the participating stakeholders in one of the 6 Bio-based Education Centres (BBECs), specifically:

- Mediterranean Europe
- North-West Europe – Finland
- North-West Europe – Denmark
- North-West Europe – Ireland
- Central - Eastern Europe (Poland and the Czech Republic)
- Central - Eastern Europe - Germany

The value proposition for each of the BBECs has been tailored taking into consideration the geographical specificities and needs of each region: a brief presentation of the key characteristics, business models and governance structures of the BBECs was also provided during the workshop.

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Figure 3: Highlight from the workshop - Presentation of the 6 Regional BBECs Business Models

The final part of the workshop was dedicated to an interactive panel discussion, engaging the participating stakeholders in an exercise to identify possible collaborations, in light of the implementation and replication of the BBECs.

The discussion was animated by asking:

- What is your interest in the BBEC?
- How the BBECs could be implemented/replicated in your context?

The inputs provided by the participants were collected through a [MIRO board](#) and the following tables resume the main outcomes with the key contacts and responsible partners per each BBEC.

During the interactive exercise, in addition to the possibility to express an interest in one of more specific regional BBECs, the stakeholders were also able to locate themselves at a more transversal European level.

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Figure 4: Screenshot of the MIRO board

After the first IRWG workshop, several stakeholders expressed spontaneous interest in being part of the IRWG, with the consequent signature of a Letter of Support in which they ensured a commitment to the implementation of the BBECs in their region.

4.4. Outcomes collected in the MIRO board

The following tables resume the outcomes collected through MIRO board and divided per each BBEC, showing also the responsible partners per each regional Center.

European level	
What is your interest in the BBEC?	<p>CMQ Bioeco: We are campus of trades and qualifications in bioeconomy field pilot by University of Reims Champagne Ardenne, France. We would like to share our experiences and learn from yours. We are also interested in developing our international network, develop Erasmus and other opportunities for our students and teachers.</p>
	<p>Contributing to increase collaboration on education for the green transition at EU level and build capacity (in line with the Council recommendation on learning for the green transition and sustainable development) (EU Commission Education for Climate Coalition https://education-for-climate.ec.europa.eu/community/), "https://education-for-climate.ec.europa.eu/community/"</p>
	<p>Cluster SPRING - engage with stakeholders and disseminate bioeconomy. It operates mainly in Italy but interested also at European level</p>

	<p>University of Zagreb Faculty of Agriculture Branka Šakić Bobić: Increase bioeconomy knowledge of our students, improve curricula</p> <p>Potential case study for implementing GreenComp, the European Sustainability competence framework https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC128040, https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC128040"</p> <p>Creating and sharing knowledge around circular bioeconomy --> turn this knowledge into practice through education and training activities</p> <p>I am a Bioeconomy Ambassador and I want to use my role to empower organization like yours to reach out to young people. My name is Carmen Sciotti.</p> <p>As company Lenzing, we already offer one-day on site trainings for students, which are part of curricula of Austrian Universities of (Applied) Sciences. We are willing to expand the program to a wider audience. There is also on-site supervision of PhD and Masterstudents in cooperation with European Universities (who grant the academic title). Support by Biobec would be welcome to put this on a broader basis (currently, only two to three persons in the company can offer these trainings). Trian the trainers program sounds interesting.</p> <p>My name is Federica I. I am an anthropologist with a background in international development. Hence, I am strongly interested in boosting engagement of local NGOs and associations</p>
How the BBECs could be implemented/repl icated in your context?	<p>The Coe BBE is located in the south of the Netherlands. It is a research and education focussed initiatives with strong links to companies and governments. It acts already 10 years as a BBEC.</p> <p>Read about us here Meet our Bioeconomy Youth Ambassadors! (europa.eu) we have a diverse set of competences and live all over Europe,"https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/news/all-research-and-innovation-news/meet-our-bioeconomy-youth-ambassadors-2022-08-04_en"</p>

Mediterranean Europe	
<p>Key responsible for the BBEC: Davide Viaggi - davide.viaggi@unibo.it; Giacomo Maria Rinaldi - giacomomaria.rinaldi2@unibo.it</p>	
<p>What is your interest in the BBEC?</p>	<p>Anastasio J. V. (IFAPA-Institute of Agricultural and Fisheries Research and Training, Spain) Researcher with university teaching duties on the field of circular bioeconomy, specialized in agri-food and environmental economics and policy. I collaborate with the Andalusian Cluster of Circular Bioeconomy (coordinated by IFAPA and the regional government), which is expected to start soon, and has training (at different levels) at its cent., https://www.unia.es/cursos/guias/Folleto_3966_Experto_subproductos.pdf, https://www.imrd.ugent.be/, https://www.bioeconomiaandalucia.es/cluster-de-bioeconomia"</p>

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	<p>I'm a university. I think BBEC should contribute to teachers and trainers' competences update. It's difficult to find positions to directly know what's happening in the companies.</p>
	<p>Cluster SPRING - engage with stakeholders and disseminate bioeconomy</p>
	<p>IRELANDS NATIONAL CLUSTER IRISH BIOECONOMY FOUNDATION</p>
	<p>In Food Hub SRL SB we have 3 areas. I think that the most important for this project is the one that is about Dissemination, Communication, Education and Exploitation. We are the bigger Italian Agri-Food Tech Community and we are surrounded by a network of Experts who ensure the quality of our information and training offer.</p>
	<p>Rebeca R. I am working in a Technological center (TECNOVA) as a head of two department. I would like to know more about the competences and the training process of student (bachelor and master, mainly). We are interested on biotechnology and bio-based products.</p>
	<p>We are currently mapping innovation in the Italian agri-food sector, and we are going to expand this project to Europe in the future. The output of the project is a database, as well as a report, that will be useful to understand how innovation is evolving in our sector. The aim is to create the right link between different players in order to facilitate the innovation in our sector.</p>
	<p>I'm university researcher and I would like involving myself and/or my team (post-doc, PhD students) in BBEC activities (educational but also training activities) I'm university researcher and I would like involving myself and/or my team (post-doc, PhD students) in BBEC activities (educational but also training activities). Our interest is in field of industrial biotechnology, biorefinery design and bio-based products. ISABELLA P. UNIVERSITY OF BARI</p>
	<p>Teacher and researcher from University of Seville (Spain). Nowadays, coordinator of a project focus on the incorporation of circular economy in the Economy teaching</p>
	<p>BioökonomieREVIER is a cross sectoral transformation cluster in the coal phase our region Rhenish Revier in western Germany. We are focussing on implementing a circular and integrated regional bioeconomy (model region). We want to network with European bioeconomy initiatives and are located at Forschungszentrum Jülich.</p>
	<p>We are Sardegna Ricerche, regional agency, we are not educational entity</p>
	<p>Frangiskos K. (National Technical University of Athens) I will be happy to have Educational Material from BIObec</p>
How the BBECs could be	<p>TECNOVA: Having a strong connection among the different agents involved, and creating a platform to be in contact</p>

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implemented/replicated in your context?	PAOLA P. Univ Teramo work on training students - bioeconomy - agrifood - consortium for a in Erasmus Traineeship Starting from regional industry-research clusters Setting initiatives to sensibilise/fertilise the possible target actors
	I would like use BBEC platform in order to share our project results. For example, I think to MSCA public engagement activities or other projects with multidisciplinary approaches involving research but also policymaker and other stakeholder.
	I work at the Department of Applied Economics at the University of Seville (Spain). I think that we can add BBEC into our activities (mbmarinus.es)
	Frangiskos K. (National Technical University of Athens) can contribute in addition to my expertise in Industrial Biotechnology with Long Life Educational Courses In Bioeconomy & Biotechnology/ Bioethics as well as Biotechnology and Biolaw

North-West Europe – Finland

Key responsible for the BBEC: Katri Rusanen- katri.rusanen@uef.fi; Jouni Pykäläinen - jouni.pykalainen@uef.fi

What is your interest in the BBEC?	I'm curious about this Hub, because I am organizing a Biobased Battle between Universities of Applied Sciences of Finland and The Netherlands (end goal: Living Lab)
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North-West Europe – Denmark

Key responsible for the BBEC: Knud Tybirk - kt@foodbiocluster.dk

North-West Europe – Ireland

Key responsible for the BBEC: Eve Savage - eve.savage@mtu.ie; Helena McMahon - helena.mcmahon@mtu.ie

What is your interest in the BBEC?	Kevin Ryan Project Manager Irish Bioeconomy Foundation
	I'm university researcher and I would like involving myself and/or my team (post-doc, PhD students) in BBEC activities (educational but also training activities) ISABELL P. UNIVERSITY OF BARI
	Eve.Savage@mtu.ie Higher Education University and directors of Ireland's Knowledge Centre for Climate Carbon & Community Action (IKC3)
	IRELANDS NATIONAL CLUSTER IRISH BIOECONOMY FOUNDATION
	Manager at the bioeconomy cluster in Ireland. The cluster is focused on strengthening collaboration between researchers, technology providers, and industry – from SMEs to Multinationals

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	<p>– to develop, scale and internationalise next generation bio-based products, services and value chains, whilst in tandem driving forward to transition to a low carbon economy.</p> <p>Head of Research at SHANNON ABC research centre which provides tailored solutions for organisations wishing to maximize and diversify existing value chains for sectors including marine, bioplastics, bioeconomy, food and agriculture.</p> <p>Director of CIRC BIO Research Group, a multidisciplinary expertise across all areas of the bioeconomy including bioresource modelling, value chain development, bioprocessing and extraction technologies, new product development, business model development and innovation management.</p> <p>Head of School of STEM operating in the key areas of biotechnology, mechatronic and sensor engineering as well as eco-tourism among others and has developed links and strategic alliances with regional and national industrial and educational partners to continue to develop and enhance programme provision and progression opportunities.</p> <p>Kieran O'Donoghue - AGRITECH CLUSTER facilitating engagement between agricultural technology industry partners, research and academia.</p> <p>Chief Executive Officer of bioeconomy cluster in Ireland. The cluster promotes the conversion of natural resources to high value products for the development of a sustainable bioeconomy in Ireland.</p>
How the BBECs could be implemented/replicated in your context?	<p>I would like use BBEC platform in order to share our project results. For example, I think to MSCA public engagement activities or other projects with multidisciplinary approaches involving research but also policymaker and other stakeholder.</p> <p>Ireland has a strong bioeconomy network including a number of research centres and clusters focussed on bioeconomy including CBCSW, CircBio, IBF, BiOrbic, the National Cluster Network, EI Technology Gateways and Nua Na Mara.</p> <p>Ireland has a number of funding bodies including Science Foundation Ireland (SFI), Enterprise Ireland and InterTradeIreland with a portfolio of collaborative funding mechanisms that can be activated for the bioeconomy sector.</p> <p>Ireland's government is committed to the development of the bioeconomy, in particular the Department of Agriculture, Food & Marine (DAFM) and Department of Environment, Climate & Communications (DECC).</p> <p>Site visits to other European countries organised by MTU/ IBF through networks from European projects including BIObec.</p> <p>Many of the educational applications, programmes and services are scalable and replicable through the extensive networks held by MTU & IBF across the Higher Education and Further Education ecosystem.</p> <p>Providing unified support with grant and funding proposal writing for submission and consortium building for both research and commercial projects.</p>

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	Access to results of European projects and scientific journals to allow implementation of biobased solutions on a regional scale to facilitate cohesive vision, new projects and build upon existing data and developments.
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Central - Eastern Europe (Poland and the Czech Republic)

Key responsible for the BBEC: Damian Kuznowicz - d.kuznowicz@procvivis.org.pl; George Sakellaris - g.sakellaris@gmail.com

What is your interest in the BBEC?	EPRD We would like to contribute in consulting services, project management, creating consortiums for bioeconomy projects
	Magdalena K. Institute of Biochemistry and Biophysics Polish Academy of Sciences (IBB PAS). We would like to service PhD studies on the bioeconomy thematic pillars in cooperation with industry, interlinking academic institution with students and industry, popularizing science in scholars and at various types of public events.
	My name is Dawid B. and I represent the University of Agriculture in Kracow. We are in the process of preparing a bioeconomy textbook as one of a result of the implementation of the Erasmus+ project
	BIOEAST Thematic Working Group initiated by the BIOEAST Initiative - the macro regional group focused on the education coordinated by the BIOEAST HUB CZ is supporting the Central and Easter BioBec Centre. You can get in touch with us on www.bio-hub.cz , " https://bioeast.eu/download/bioeast_a4_leporello_02_education_print/ ", https://www.bioeast.eu/ , https://www.bio-hub.cz/ "
How the BBECs could be implemented/replicated in your context?	Magdalena K. (IBB PAS) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • expertise in the following bioeconomy sectors: food, medical products, renewable energy, (biofuels), sewage treatment, agriculture (microbial fertilizers); • experience in teaching PhD students; • innovation activities; - collaboration with industrial partners; • popularization of science

Central - Eastern Europe (Germany)

Key responsible for the BBEC: Lina Mayorga - lina.mayorgaduarte@uni-hohenheim.de; Iris Lewandowski - iris_lewandowski@uni-hohenheim.de

What is your interest in the BBEC?	I'm university researcher and I would like involving myself and/or my team (post-doc, PhD students) in BBEC activities (educational but also training activities). Our interest is in field of industrial biotechnology, biorefinery design and bio-based products. ISABELLA P. UNIVERSITY OF BARI
	IRELANDS NATIONAL CLUSTER IRISH BIOECONOMY FOUNDATION
	I'm an academic research centre at the heart of a biorefinery. It brings together the complementary scientific and technical

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	expertise of about 90 researchers (green chemistry, biomaterials, etc.). We train in research through research doctoral students (30 per year), post-doctoral students (15 per year) and interns (30 per year) We also have a third-place activity. Industrialists, the general public and local authorities come together to discuss the bioeconomy, visit our center or the biorefinery. We would like to be involved in making the network benefit from the ecosystem of our center.
How the BBECs could be implemented/replicated in your context?	I would like use BBEC platform in order to share our project results. For example, I think to MSCA public engagement activities or other projects with multidisciplinary approaches involving research but also policymaker and other stakeholder. connect industry and training

4.5. Follow-up of the workshop

As a follow-up of the workshop, an info package was sent to all the registered participants including:

- PDFs collecting the slides presented, with useful links.
- The key contacts of each Bio-Based Education Centre (BBEC)
- The link to the MIRO Board used during the interactive session, to see the outcomes and collect further contributions up to a week after the conclusion of the workshop.

The responsible partners SIE also created a [new section on BIObec website](#) dedicated to the workshop, collecting all the above-mentioned materials to make them publicly available for consultation and download.

The coordinator UNIBO, in collaboration with FVA is now performing a selection of the most relevant stakeholders to be invited to be part of the IRWG. Those stakeholders will be directly contacted and invited to sign the LOS.

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5. Liaison with other projects and initiatives

As part of the stakeholder engagement activities, BIObec promotes the collaboration and cross-fertilisation with other ongoing projects and initiatives to maximise the impact of project's activities and efforts towards the creation of an innovation ecosystem for the bioeconomy education, through effective educational Centres.

The following paragraphs describe in detail the collaborations established.

5.1. Collaboration with relevant concluded and ongoing projects and initiatives

BIObec builds on the outcomes of several concluded and ongoing projects and initiatives that were key to inform the activities that took place in the first 15 months of the project. This type of collaboration ensured that EU funded projects' exploitable assets were capitalised, preventing overlapping among the projects' activities and results (see following table).

Projects and initiatives	Partner(s) involved
H2020-BBI-2018: URBIOFUTURE - Boosting future careers, education and research activities in the European bio-based industry.	UAB, CNR, CTA, FBCD, SIE, IHE
Erasmus Plus KA203 - Strategic Partnerships for higher education: ABBEE - Accelerating the transition towards the Bio-Based Economy via Education.	WU, UHOH, UEF
H2020-BBI-2017: ICT BIOCHAIN - ICT Tools in Efficient Biomass Supply Chains for Sustainable Chemical Production.	CTA, SIE, IBF, ITT
H2020-BBI-2018: LIFT - Benefit from previous and current work to create a coherent and stimulating 'environment' for a sustainable bio-based industry in Europe.	FVA
H2020-FNR-2020: Transition2BIO – Support the transition towards the bioeconomy for a more sustainable future through communication, education and public engagement.	FVA, UNIBO (on behalf of the entire European Bioeconomy University)
H2020-BBI-2016: GRACE - GRowing Advanced industrial Crops on marginal lands for biorEfineries.	UHOH, WU
H2020-INFRAIA-2017: IBISBA – Industrial Biotechnology Innovation and Synthetic Biology Accelerator.	WU, UAB, CNR
H2020-BBI-2019: MpowerBIO - Empower SME clusters to bring SMEs 'across the valley of death'.	FBCD, CTA, SIE, IBF,
H2020-BB-2017: BIOVOICES – Mobilization of a plurality of voices and mutual learning to accelerate the Bio-based sector.	WU, CNR, FVA
H2020-BB-2017: BLOOM - Strategies for improving the bioeconomy knowledge of the general public.	WU
H2020-BBI-2017: BIOBRIDGES - Establish cooperation and partnership with brand owners and consumer representatives to improve the market access of sustainable bio-based products.	FVA
EIT RawMaterials: RM@Schools - Raw Matter Ambassador at Schools 3.0.	CNR

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EIT Raw Materials: SmartPlaCE@Schools - Serious game Platform for education on Circular Economy in high schools.	CNR
Erasmus Plus KA203 - Strategic Partnerships for higher education: FOEBE - FOstering Entrepreneurship for the BioEconomy.	APT, UNIBO,UHOH, UEF, BOKU,WU
Erasmus Plus KA203 - Strategic Partnerships for higher education: EBU student journey: Bioeconomy qualification supplement.	UHOH UNIBO,APT, UEF, BOKU,WU
Erasmus Mundus Joint Master Degree: BIOCEB – European Master in Biological and Chemical Engineering for a Sustainable Bioeconomy.	APT
H2020-RUR-2019: BIOEASTsUP - Advancing Sustainable Circular Bioeconomy in Central and Eastern European countries.	ART
H2020-RUR-2017: NEXTFOOD - Educating the next generation of professionals in the agrifood system.	UNIBO

Table 4: List of collaboration with relevant concluded and ongoing projects and initiatives

5.2. Collaboration with the European Bioeconomy Network

BIObec joined the European Bioeconomy Network, a proactive alliance of around 120 projects and initiatives¹ dealing with Bioeconomy promotion, communication and support.

With its active participation, BIObec contributes in consolidating the EuBioNet robust position in stimulating the debate and delivering recommendations, position papers and policy briefs to increase its effectiveness in contributing to the transition towards the circular bioeconomy in Europe.

The updated European Bioeconomy Strategy addressed the Education issue as “Promote education training and skills across the Bioeconomy”. In fact, education at all levels has been identified as the main driver for the deployment of sustainable and circular bioeconomy to facilitate economic transition and to meet the current needs of the developing bioeconomy and the move to carbon neutrality by 2050. For this reason, a working group in bioeconomy education was established within the EuBioNet and BIObec is part of the key players involved in the group, with the aim to map the future skills needed in bioeconomy and provide recommendations on how address the above-mentioned challenges.

Within the EuBioNet working group in bioeconomy education several activities already took place with the involvement of BIObec and are resumed in the following table.

Activity	Date	How the collaboration took place
KOM of the EuBioNet working group in bioeconomy education	22 March 2021	MML to define vision, objectives and expected outcomes of the EuBioNet educational working group. Although BIObec was in the GA preparation phase, several partners participated to the KOM.
Status and Future of Bioeconomy Education – Learning from EU projects	19 November 2021	Speech at the workshop organized by the EuBioNet and the Association for European Life Science Universities and the European Community of

¹ Number of EuBioNet members updated at 21/11/2022.

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		Practice for Bioeconomy Education with the aim to consolidate the current perspective for innovation in education for the Bioeconomy at all levels.
Paving the way towards Sustainable Entrepreneurship Education	15 March 2022	Co-organisation of the workshop with the EuBioNet, Transition2BIO, the European Community of Practice for Bioeconomy Education, BIOSKILLS and the European Bioeconomy University (EBU). The workshop involved projects and initiatives interested in the intersection of Entrepreneurship Education (EE) and Sustainable Education (SE), with a special focus on circular and sustainable bioeconomy. The aim was to identify how the cross-fertilisation of EE and SE can help design educational curricula and extra-curricular activities for sustainability-minded entrepreneurs of tomorrow.
Projects2Projects	5 October 2022	Support to the workshop organised by the EuBioNet, in collaboration with the European Commission, Transition2BIO, BIOEAST, BioGov.net, GenB projects. The aim was to maximise the exploitation of lessons learnt and heritage of H2020 bioeconomy projects in communication, education and stakeholder engagement to effectively kick-off the newly funded Horizon Europe ones. The workshop was an official side event of the high-level Bioeconomy Conference organised by the EC on 6/7 October 2022 for the 10 years of the bioeconomy strategy. In this context, BIObec was presented in the thematic working group in Bioeconomy education and communication.

Table 5: List of activities organised in the context of the EuBioNet working group in bioeconomy education, involving BIObec

5.3. Collaborations established

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Since bioeconomy and education are typically crosscutting issues, a number of synergies and collaborations were established during the first 15 months of the project in order to:

- promote the collaboration and cross-fertilisation with other ongoing projects and initiatives to maximise the impact of project's activities and efforts toward the creation of an innovation ecosystem for the bioeconomy education, through effective educational Centres
- facilitate the co-organisation of joint activities among projects and promote the exchange of knowledge and good practices
- animate the debate around challenges and gaps still to be addressed
- ensure the connection and collaboration with expert groups (like the BIC experts group in education), to timely transfer the lessons learnt and scale-up the impacts
- explore synergies in terms of communication and participation to other projects' activities.

A large number of connections and collaborations have been established, in particular:

- Joint meetings with several projects in bioeconomy education, e.g. Bioskills tender, Transition2BIO, BIOEAST initiative, European Bioeconomy University (EBU) and Bioeconomy Education Community of Practice
- Connections with the new Horizon Europe projects BioGov.net, Engage4BIO, GenB, BioBeo, BIOMODEL4REGIONS, in light of future collaboration
- Meetings with the Italian Ministry of Education to make sure BIObec is among the projects and initiatives involved in the working group in bioeconomy education in Italy
- Participation as a speaker at various conferences, events and workshops organised by other projects (see table 4).

To strengthen the impact of these collaborations, BIObec took an active role in the co-organisation and participation in the following activities:

Main organisers	Date	How the collaboration took place
Transition2BIO, BIOEAST and GoDanuBIO	6-7 April 2022	BIObec supported the organization of the capacity building program for regional actors on bioeconomy communication, education and stakeholder engagement
Lazio Innova, Transition2BIO, EuBioNet, Novamont, Cluster SPRING and Resoil Foundation	Academic Year 2021/2022	BIObec is partner of the Startupper School Academy competition 2022 - special "Bioeconomy" prize. The aim of this activity was to raise awareness of students for a more sustainable economic model that uses renewable resources as an alternative to the fossil ones. The activity included training for teachers and high school students.

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Promoting education, training and skills across the bioeconomy – 1 st workshop	26 October 2021	BIObec delivered two speeches (Davide Viaggi and Susanna Albertini) at the workshop organized by BIOSKILLS tender, together with the European Commission's Directorate General for Research & Innovation (DG RTD).
Promoting education, training and skills across the bioeconomy – 2 nd workshop	26 April 202	BIObec delivered a speech (Susanna Albertini) to the second workshop organized by BIOSKILLS tender, together with the European Commission's Directorate General for Research & Innovation (DG RTD).
Transition2BIO projects, with the support of the Circular Bio-based Europe Joint Undertaking (CBE JU)	September 2022- November 2022	BIObec co-organised the “Young Bioeconomy Entrepreneurs” joint social media campaign. The campaign consisted in the co-production of a series of video interviews. The aim of this initiative was to inspire, inform and attract young generations towards educational and working careers in the bioeconomy, therefore contributing to raise the future generation of workforce informed and interested in this domain.
BIC working group in bioeconomy education	Throughout the duration of the project	BIObec established a connection and collaboration with the BIC experts group in education to timely transfer the lessons learnt and scale-up the impacts, through dedicated meetings with Nelo Emerencia.

Table 6: Events and initiatives jointly organised by BIObec with other projects and initiatives

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6. Conclusions and next steps

The engagement of stakeholders is a central activity for the BIObec project, ensuring that the results are relevant and actionable by the stakeholders in their practice.

For this reason, a dedicated task will guarantee this activity is undertaken seriously throughout the entire duration of the project, facilitating the consultation and involvement of stakeholders in all BIObec's activities.

During the second half of the project, considering that the project is delivering concrete outcomes that are interesting for the stakeholders, this activity will follow BIObec progression and pave the way towards effective exploitation of its results.

In this context, the second IRWG international workshop will be organised on M20 to facilitate the adoption, implementation and replication of the BBECs by the stakeholders engaged. The workshop will attract a wider international audience, including stakeholders from less mature regions (e.g. the Eastern countries).

Finally, on M28 the Capacity building activity, organised under WP4, will involve the IRWG members in a Mobilisation and Mutual Learning activity to provide actionable recommendations and guidelines to be consolidated in the final BIObec toolkit.

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7. Annex

7.1. Annex 1: Letter of Support

To:

Prof. Davide Viaggi
Alma Mater Studiorum – Università di Bologna
Bologna, Italy

LETTER OF SUPPORT

Hereby, I [name], in my quality of [role] of the [firm name], declare our interest in fully supporting the project BIObec coordinated by prof. Davide Viaggi (UNIBO) and funded by the Bio Based Industries Joint Undertaking (JU) under grant agreement No 101023381.

[Brief description of the firm]

BIObec will develop a holistic framework for multi-level Bio-Based Education Centres (BBEC) that will allow to answer the present and future needs of the industry and of the surrounding ecosystem at local, regional and/or national levels.

Notably, a major objective of BIObec is to guarantee the replicability of the BBEC experience in other European regions and countries through a process of stakeholder engagement and the co-development of a roadmap applicable for potential additional BBECs across Europe.

The project's objectives are in line with the ongoing activities of [firm name] in relation to the education and professional orientation ongoing programmes and will contribute to innovate the biobased education framework through an integrated multi-sectorial and multi-stakeholder strategy.

In particular, [firm name] is glad to provide support to the BIObec project and will participate to the “**Implementation and Replication Working Groups**” (IRWGs) of the project. More specifically, the involvement will concern:

- participation in project's workshops by delivering information on current needs and potential solutions;
- collaboration in the exploitation of the results of the project by exploring the opportunity of transfer the provided novel education framework into the territorial bioeconomy Ecosystem;
- collaboration to the dissemination of the project results and communication materials through its channels.

The participation in the BIObec project is voluntary and we reserve the right to cancel it at any time.

We understand that this letter of support is non-binding and simply demonstrates recognition of the importance and support to the BIObec project initiative.

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We also understand that our participation does not imply a financial contribution apart from the reimbursement of expenses (e.g. travel and accommodation when attending workshops or meetings), and that we may not have access to confidential consortium documents such as internal meeting reports.

Your Sincerely,

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7.2. Annex 2: Value proposition for the engagement of IRWG members

BIObec is looking for stakeholders to be part of the Implementation and Replication Working Group (IRWG) for the design of Bio-Based Education Centers (BBECs)

The BIObec project

BIObec is a project funded by BBI JU under Horizon 2020 aiming at leveraging education to unlock the full potential of the European bioeconomy. BIObec is bringing together 19 partners from 12 different countries that will work for 30 months and build bridges between the bio-based industry and the education system.

The Bio-Based Education Centers

BIObec concept merges the traditional idea of an education centre – such as a university or a vocational education and training centre – with that of a knowledge hub: the Bio-Based Education Centres (BBECs), which will act as multi-level knowledge hubs bridging the gaps between academic institutions, students, innovation entities and policymakers.

BIObec seeks to set the basis for the development of BBECs in six different European regions to answer the needs of the bio-based industry at local, regional, and national levels. These BBECs are expected to ensure a wide geographical coverage in Europe and address a wide range of topics linked to the variety of value chains and the different institutional contexts, paving the way for replication in other regions.

What is the Implementation and Replication Working Group (IRWG)

The IRWG will participate to project initiatives in the role of stakeholders and will be the core nucleus for the future implementation of the BBECs as well as initiators of initiatives replicating BIObec experience beyond the project's efforts. It will be the core component of the future implementation of the BBECs.

Main IRWG Stakeholders

The multi-stakeholders IRWG will involve Regions and BioRegions, industrial clusters, industries, educational providers (at different levels, covering vocational training, university and post university curricula, on-the-job training and life-long learning), NGOs and associations of primary producers, multipliers, public administration, Digital Innovation Hubs.

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Benefits for the participating stakeholders in the IRWG

The stakeholders actively participating to BIObec IRWG will:

- “Make their voice heard” in the design of the multi-level Bio-Based Education Centers (BBECs), by providing their expectations, needs, requirements, opportunities and barriers.
- Make sure that the BIOBEC project's outcomes are actionable in their context, considering present and future needs of the industry and of the surrounding ecosystem at local, regional, national and/or international levels.
- Get first hand insights with regards to the setup of bioeconomy education centres and have direct access to good practices and case studies in different European Countries
- Have the possibility to be engaged in the co-design of the BBEC in 6 European Countries towards wide implementation and replication of the format in different countries and levels (local, regional, national).

Do you want to know more?

Please contact the BIObec partner responsible for Stakeholder Engagement

FVA New Media Research – Italy

Susanna Albertini – albertini@fvaweb.it

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7.3. Annex 3: Agenda of the first IRWG workshop

BIObec Implementation and Replication Working Group workshop 21 October 2022 Workshop on-line 10:00-11:30 CET

Context	<p>The BIObec project, funded by BBI JU under Horizon 2020, aims at leveraging education to unlock the full potential of the European bioeconomy, by building bridges between the bio-based industry and the education system.</p> <p>BIObec concept merges the traditional idea of an education centre – such as a university or a vocational education and training centre – with that of a knowledge hub: the Bio-Based Education Centres (BBECs), which will act as multi-level knowledge hubs bridging the gaps between academic institutions, students, innovation entities and policymakers.</p> <p>BIObec seeks to set the basis for the development of BBECs in six different European regions to answer the needs of the bio-based industry at local, regional, and national levels. These BBECs are expected to ensure a wide geographical coverage in Europe and address a wide range of topics linked to the variety of value chains and the different institutional contexts, paving the way for replication in other regions.</p> <p>The core nucleus for the future implementation of the BBECs is the Implementation and Replication Working Group (IRWG), that will participate to project initiatives in the role of stakeholders and will facilitate the replication of the BIObec's experience beyond the project's efforts.</p> <p>The IRWG members are local stakeholders, interested in implementing and replicating the BBECs experience in other EU Regions and countries by co-developing a roadmap applicable for potential additional BBECs across Europe.</p>
Objectives	<p>The first IRWG workshop will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • stimulate the discussion around bioeconomy education • define a more integrated, connected and wider approach for the BBECs future implementation • explore the opportunity to transfer and replicate the BBECs formats into additional territorial bioeconomy ecosystems • engage additional IRWG members
Format	Online Mobilisation and Mutual Learning workshop.
Target participants	Current and future IRWG members.
Registration	https://forms.gle/7PsuemSCG5jqU89FA

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Agenda:

10.00-10.05 (5 mins)	<p>Purpose of the IRWG workshop (FVA) Overview of the BIObec project (UNIBO):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The role of BIObec in bioeconomy education • The role of the IRWG
10.05-10.15 (10 mins)	Overview of EU funded projects in bioeconomy education, targeting different levels of education (FVA)
10.15-10.30 (15 mins)	Overview of current needs (UAB) Inspirational case studies (UHOH)
10.30-10.50 (20 mins)	<p>The 6 BBECs (UEF + responsible partners):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • graphical overview of the BBECs and the related Countries • brief presentations of the key characteristics, business model and governance structures of the BBECs
10.50-11.20 (30 mins)	<p>Interactive panel discussion to identify possible collaborations in light of the implementation and replication of the BBECs (FVA with the support of BBECs responsible):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is your interest in the BBEC? • How the BBECs could be implemented/replicated in your context? • Suggest other stakeholders that we should involve.
11.20-11.30 (10 mins)	Next steps (FVA + UNIBO)

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